

PROFESSIONAL APPROACH AND CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN LINGUISTIC TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the challenges of intercultural communication in the context of growing global ties. The author makes the case that language instruction should have a professional focus and emphasizes the need of providing sociocultural knowledge to students studying international relations, management, and economics during their language training. Understanding how individuals from many cultures communicate with one another is the foundation of cross-cultural communication. Furthermore, it is expected to generate some suggestions that can assist individuals from many cultures interact more effectively with one another.

Keywords: *cross-cultural communication; cross-cultural barrier; globalization; contextual implication; professional competence; professional international communication.*

International specialists receive professional language training using a blend of sociocultural, linguistic, and communicative approaches. A phased professional language program is methodically presented, and it is effective in the setting of an established educational professional language communicative environment. Innovative pedagogical technologies are used to teach intercultural communication. The study of how individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds interact with one another—both in ways that are similar to and different from one another—as well as how they make an effort to communicate across cultural barriers is known as cross-cultural communication. Intercultural communication is one field of study that is comparable (Fuller & Toon, 1988).

The philosophy and methods of professional education in the area of teaching foreign languages can be developed using this idea. Globally, the function and caliber of international communication have evolved in the twenty-first century. The expansion of international relations and the involvement of many employees of national and international companies in international communication have been brought about in recent decades by the development of communication technologies and the globalization of the economy. Examples of these employees include

managers, public relations specialists, lawyers, financiers, economists, managers, media representatives, and employees of the tourism industry. Every culture values communication style highly. An interactive communication style, where you can ask questions, make remarks, express surprise or happiness, is considered typical by Americans and British people. They get cautious and believe they stated something incorrectly because their spouse doesn't seem to be asking any questions. The German way of doing things is to listen to your conversation partner before responding with questions. However, officials from Finland and Japan will bide their time to strike up a conversation. Their dialogue consists of them exchanging monologues. Allusions, half-hints, and sarcasm are hallmarks of the British. The English term "understatement" is another one to bring up. When an Englishman wants to convey a negative attitude regarding something, he will remark, "I don't think it's a very good idea." (I don't believe this is a very nice notion or thought.) Saying something like, "This is a bad idea," to convey the same message, will come out as very direct and impolite.

Representatives of our nation, which has a poorer communicative framework, frequently make the exact same error. Low communicative context representatives are reticent, talk plainly and clearly, and avoid giving room for misunderstandings. These nations include the USA, Germany, Belarus, Russia, and the Scandinavian nations. Representatives of nations with high communicative context tend to speak more verbosely; words can suggest multiple meanings; gestures and facial expressions can impact word meanings; and the speaker himself can interpret what is said in light of the context, time, and circumstance. Greece, Spain, Italy, and the Eastern countries are among those having a high level of communication. You can position France and Great Britain between them.

Leaders of multinational corporations observe that negotiators from various cultural backgrounds are unable to follow the same format. Furthermore, language—including its grammatical, phonetic, and lexical designs—as well as extralinguistic variables have a significant impact on the outcome of negotiations. This is the iceberg's buried portion. English is now widely used in business due to the effects of globalization. Many businesses nowadays claim to have a "corporate language," which is typically English. For instance, the German corporation Bauer's representative office in Moscow mandates that all staff members speak English, which serves as the business's working and corporate language. English is the official business language even at the Russian fashion designer V. Yudashkin's company. This holds true for both foreigners negotiating in another language—such as English—and cross-cultural representatives for whom English serves as the official

business language. We hear information coming at us verbally while we're speaking with business partners. [Gradobitova, Piskunova, 2005]

This is the point at which comprehension may become difficult. Differing linguistic intonation contours and melodies can cause a misinterpretation of the situation. The issues surrounding intercultural communication are seen by S. G. Ter-Minasova, an Honorary Professor at Moscow State University M.V. Lomonosov, as a "war of cultures" in which there are no winners or losers. She believes that the development of unique teaching tools, such as case studies and role-playing games, is essential to preparing students for intercultural communication. And the task of teachers is to prepare students for an adequate perception of typical sociocultural situations, and first of all, situations of business culture.

In addition, educators ought to instruct students on how to research and evaluate a prospective business partner's sociocultural traits without sacrificing their own sociocultural identity, as well as how to negotiate so that both parties perceive the information appropriately. This will assist in bridging cultural gaps in work-related tasks. It is important to first define intercultural communication before discussing the issues surrounding this relatively recent development in the study and practice of teaching foreign languages. If the simplest explanation is that we are communicating with "others"—that is, individuals from different cultures with whom we engage in cross-cultural discourse. Communicating with foreign partners in a foreign language, each of us carries within us a national mentality, a vision of the world characteristic of our ethnoculture, and at the same time faces a different logic of worldview, a way of thinking expressed in the mentality of a bearer of another ethnoculture. [Kart,Fox, 2005]

The issue of intercultural communication emerged in the latter part of the 20th century when contacts in the domains of politics, science, and culture increased along with the expansion of international trade. However, professionals who worked overseas frequently came across representatives of different cultural communities who had inaccurate notions of everyday and professional communication circumstances. This led to issues with professional communication as well as domestic disputes. Over time, it became apparent that training in intercultural communication—that is, familiarity with everyday cultural practices, norms, and traditions—was just as important for international relations professionals as training in foreign languages.

The communication process can be condensed to the following chain to represent it: idea: open to receiving information; heard; deciphered; comprehended; perceived. Every step of the information transfer process could result in information leakage or distortion if the second communicant is not proactive in understanding and

is not engaging in counter-mental activity. Edgar Rubin's illustration of a white vase on a black background illustrates how information is not always seen in an obvious way: some people see a white vase, while others see two black profiles. A circumstance that is very similar to this one arises during oral communication. Most of the time, each communicant knows what he believes to be true. The most extreme example is the game "damaged telephone," where the final player frequently only gets a small portion of the initial data. Comparable procedures take place in international, or intercultural, communication.

Language is an essential component of culture, which encompasses not just literature and art but also an ethnic group's shared values, connections, and standards of behavior. While some are readily apparent, others are concealed. An iceberg model is frequently used as an example to depict the visible and hidden facets of culture. Food, dress, and behavior are examples of tangible forms. Values, beliefs, implications, and attitudes regarding different phenomena are examples of hidden ones. Language reflects types of culture, both overt and covert. Together, language and culture paint a linguistic portrait of the world that is unique to a certain ethnic group. Speech activity is conducted in a wide social setting within the context of professional communication, which establishes the statement's actual meaning. Semantic barriers in communication can arise as a result of disparities in speech behavior and mindset.

To sum up, language is a tool used in communication to transmit concepts and data. Gaining a respect for the many concepts associated with a certain group is quite important. Interaction is facilitated by the use of language as a tool for communication between people. Conversely, it has been noted that language use leads to a more accurate self-perception and a deeper understanding of oneself. Overcoming social barriers in an environment where several cultures live closely requires the capacity to speak with folks from different communities in a fluent and easy manner. Nonetheless, people can still communicate with one another even if they do not speak the same language. The problem of professional language training for international relations specialists has specific theoretical, methodological, and applied components that science has the ability to enhance. Analyses are done on the process of forming a professional identity as well as professional language training concerns. A modern international specialist's professional language training is seen as the process and outcome of developing professionally significant competencies that enable a person to engage in foreign language-speaking professional activities in the global community.

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